

SOME DEDEKIND η -FUNCTION IDENTITIES GENERATED BY
MICHAEL SOMOS AND ITS APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT. This study involves the new approach to the theta function identities discovered by Michael Somos using PARI/GP scripts and offer no proofs for them. The mentioned identities are analogous to the identities discovered by S. Ramanujan. In this paper, we prove some of these identities of level 10 given by M. Somos concerning η -functions and also we extract the colored partition identities for the same.

1. Introduction

Srinivasa Ramanujan in his notebook [3] recorded 23 identities that involves the ratio of Dedekind η -function while were later proved by Berndt and Zhang [2] by utilizing Ramanujan's modular equations of various degree. Motivated by the work of Ramanujan, Somos [9] used a computer to discover almost 6200 Dedekind η -function identities and he used the PARI/GP scripts to make sure each identity is equivalent to an P - Q modular equation form without offering proof for them. Later, Yuttanan [15] proved some of these identities and also, generated interesting colored partition identities for the same. Furthermore, Vasuki and Veerasha [14] have provided proofs for η -function identities discovered by Somos of level 14 and Srivatsa kumar and veerasha [10] have developed certain partition identities for the same. Also, Srivatsa Kumar and Anuradha [11] have proved Somos's η -function identities of level 10 and B. R. Srivatsa Kumar et al. [12, 13], have successfully proven identities at different levels and developed colored partition identities for them.

Motivated by the above work, the aim of this paper is to prove some of η -function identities of level 10 generated by Somos and extract the colored partition identities for them. In Section 2 records some preliminaries. In Section 2, we prove theta-function identities of level 10. Furthermore, in section 3, we given colored partitions for some these identities.

1.1. Preliminaries. Throughout the paper, we assume that $|q| < 1$ and use the standard product notation

$$(\delta; q)_{\infty} := \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \prod_{m=1}^n (1 - \delta q^{m-1}).$$

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The general theta function $f(s, t)$ defined by Ramanujan is given by

$$f(s, t) := \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} s^{\frac{k(k+1)}{2}} t^{\frac{k(k-1)}{2}}. \quad |st| < 1.$$

The above equation in terms of Jacobi's triple product identity [1, p. 35] we have

$$f(s, t) = (-s; st)_{\infty} (-t; st)_{\infty} (st; st)_{\infty}.$$

S. Ramanujan defines the following special cases of $f(s, t)$ [1, p.36]

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(q) &:= f(q, q) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} q^{n^2} = (-q; q^2)_{\infty}^2 (q^2; q^2)_{\infty} = \frac{f_2^5}{f_1^2 f_4^2}, \\ f(-q) &:= f(-q, -q^2) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n q^{\frac{n(3n-1)}{2}} = (q; q)_{\infty} = f_1. \end{aligned}$$

Also after Ramanujan, define

$$\chi(q) := (-q; q^2)_{\infty} = \frac{f_2^2}{f_1 f_4} \quad \text{and} \quad \chi(-q) := (q; q^2)_{\infty} = \frac{f_1}{f_2}.$$

We have the expression $f(-q) = e^{-\pi i \tau / 12} \eta(\tau)$, where $\eta(\tau)$ represents the classical Dedekind eta-function for $Im(\tau) > 0$ and $q = e^{2\pi i \tau}$. The relationship that connects $f(-q)$ to $f(-q^n)$ is referred to as the theta function identity of level n . For ease of reference, we denote $f(-q^n)$ as f_n , where n is a positive integer. The various identities that involve $f(-q)$, $f(-q^2)$, $f(-q^n)$, and $f(-q^{2n})$ were established by Ramanujan in his notebook [6] and the 'Lost' notebook [7]. For instance, see [3, p.206].

$$f_1^3 f_2^3 f_5^3 f_{10}^3 + 4q^2 f_1^3 f_{10}^{10} + 3f_2^5 f_5^7 f_{10} = 4f_1 f_2^2 f_{10}^5.$$

A modular equation of degree n defined by Ramanujan, is an equation relating δ and λ that is induced by

$$\frac{{}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}; 1; 1 - \lambda\right)}{{}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}; 1; \lambda\right)} = n \frac{{}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}; 1; 1 - \delta\right)}{{}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}; 1; \delta\right)}$$

where

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(r)_n (s)_n}{(t)_n n!} z^n = {}_2F_1(r, s; t; z) \quad |z| < 1,$$

denotes an ordinary hypergeometric function with

$$\frac{\Gamma(r+k)}{\Gamma(r)} = (r)_k.$$

Then, we say that λ is of n^{th} degree over δ and call the ratio

$$\frac{z_1}{z_n} = t,$$

the multiplier, where $z_1 = {}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}; 1; \delta\right)$ and $z_n = {}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}; 1; \lambda\right)$.

Ramanujan in his notebook[6] on page 236 of his second notebook and [1, pp. 280 – 288, Entry 13(ix) and (xiv)], recorded the following modular equation of degree 5. If λ has degree five over δ and m is the multiplier for degree 5, then

$$\frac{m}{2} \left(1 + (\delta\lambda)^{1/2} + \{(1-\delta)(1-\lambda)\}^{1/2} \right) = 1 + 4^{1/3} \left(\frac{\lambda^5(1-\lambda)^5}{\delta(1-\delta)} \right)^{1/12}, \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{5}{2m} \left(1 + (\delta\lambda)^{1/2} + \{(1-\delta)(1-\lambda)\}^{1/2} \right) = 1 + 4^{1/3} \left(\frac{\delta^5(1-\delta)^5}{\lambda(1-\lambda)} \right)^{1/12} \quad (1.2)$$

and

if $P = \{16\delta\lambda(1-\delta)(1-\lambda)\}^{1/12}$ and $Q = \left\{ \frac{\lambda(1-\lambda)}{\delta(1-\delta)} \right\}^{1/8}$, then

$$Q + \frac{1}{Q} = 2 \left(\frac{1}{P} - P \right). \quad (1.3)$$

From (1.1) and (1.2), we deduce

$$m^2 \left(1 + 4^{1/3} \left(\frac{\delta^5(1-\delta)^5}{\lambda(1-\lambda)} \right)^{1/12} \right) = 5 \left(1 + 4^{1/3} \left(\frac{\lambda^5(1-\lambda)^5}{\delta(1-\delta)} \right)^{1/12} \right). \quad (1.4)$$

By employing [1, pp. 122-124, Entry 10(i) and Entry 12(v)], we transcribe (1.3) and (1.4) into theta functions and obtain

$$\frac{\chi^3(q^3)}{q^{2/3}\chi^3(q)} - \frac{\chi^2(q)\chi^2(q^3)}{q^{1/3}} + \frac{q^{2/3}\chi^3(q)}{\chi^3(q^3)} + \frac{4q^{1/3}}{\chi^2(q)\chi^2(q^3)} = 0 \quad (1.5)$$

and

$$\frac{1 + 4 \frac{q^2\chi^2(q)}{\chi^{10}(q^5)}}{1 + 4 \frac{\chi^2(q^5)}{\chi^{10}(q)}} = \frac{\varphi^4(q)}{5\varphi^4(q^5)} \quad (1.6)$$

respectively. Also one can easily see that

$$\chi(q) = \frac{(q^2; q^2)^2}{(q; q)(q^4; q^4)}; \quad \varphi(q) = \frac{(q^2; q^2)^5}{(q; q)^2(q^4; q^4)^2} \quad \text{and} \quad \chi(-q) = \frac{(q; q)}{(q^2; q^2)}. \quad (1.7)$$

From (1.7), we observe that

$$\frac{\chi^2(q)}{q^{1/3}\chi^2(q^5)} \frac{f_2}{f_{10}} = \frac{\varphi(q)}{\varphi(q^5)}. \quad (1.8)$$

For convenience, we set

$$y := y(q) = q^{-1/24}\chi(q) \quad \text{and} \quad z := z(q) = q^{-5/24}\chi(q^5).$$

2. Somos's Identities of Level 10

Theorem 2.1. *We have*

$$f_1^9 f_{10}^4 - 16q f_1 f_2^6 f_{10}^6 + 24 f_2^7 f_5^5 f_{10} - 25 f_1 f_2^4 f_5^8 = 0.$$

Proof. Multiplying (1.5) throughout by $16y^{20}z^{20}(5y^{12}+5y^{10}z^{10}+10y^{11}z^5+40yz^7+16y^2z^2+19b^{12})$ we obtain,

$$80 - \frac{160y^2}{z^{10}} + \frac{224z^2}{y^{10}} + \frac{80y^4}{z^{20}} - \frac{3360}{y^8z^8} - \frac{304z^4}{y^{20}} - \frac{1024}{y^6z^{18}} - \frac{10240}{y^{18}z^6} \\ - \frac{4096}{y^{16}z^{16}} - \frac{758}{y^9z^3} - \frac{3072}{y^7z^{13}} - \frac{3072}{y^{19}z} - \frac{12288}{y^{17}z^{11}} = 0.$$

which can be rewritten as

$$5 \left(\left(1 + \frac{4y^2}{z^{10}} \right) - 5 \left(1 + \frac{4z^2}{y^{10}} \right) \right)^2 \\ - \left(\frac{16}{y^4z^4} + \frac{24z}{y^5} \right)^2 \left(1 + \frac{4y^2}{z^{10}} \right) \left(1 + \frac{4z^2}{y^{10}} \right) = 0.$$

Employing (1.6) above, we see that

$$1 + \left(\frac{16}{y^4z^4} + \frac{24z}{y^5} \right) \frac{\varphi^2(q^5)}{\varphi^2(q)} - 25 \frac{\varphi^4(q^5)}{\varphi^4(q)} = 0.$$

Using (1.8) above, we obtain

$$1 + \left(\frac{16}{y^8} + \frac{24z^5}{y^9} \right) \left(\frac{f_{10}}{f_2} \right)^2 - \frac{25z^8}{y^8} \left(\frac{f_{10}}{f_2} \right)^4 = 0.$$

Further letting, $q \rightarrow -q$ in the preceding expression, we can express $y(-q)$ and $z(-q)$ in terms of f_n using equation (1.7). Subsequently, by multiplying the entire equation by $f_1^9 f_{10}^4$, we arrive at the desired result. \square

Theorem 2.2. *We have*

$$f_2^2 f_5^{10} + 3f_1^4 f_5^6 f_{10}^2 - 16q^2 f_1^2 f_{10}^{10} - 4f_1^3 f_2^3 f_5^3 f_{10}^3 = 0.$$

Proof. Multiplying (1.5) throughout by $20y^{-20}z^{-20}(64y^{12} - 11y^{10}z^{10} + 32z^{11}y^5 + 128y^7z + 64y^2z^2 - 4z^{12})$ we obtain,

$$-220 - \frac{1060y^2}{z^{10}} + \frac{1140z^2}{y^{10}} - \frac{200z^2}{z^5} + \frac{11120}{z^8y^8} + \frac{2400}{z^9y^3} + \frac{80z^4}{y^{20}} - \frac{2560}{z^6y^{18}} - \frac{800z^3}{y^{15}} \\ + \frac{9600}{z^7y^{13}} + \frac{1280y^4}{z^{20}} + \frac{42240}{y^6z^{18}} + \frac{12800}{yz^{19}} + \frac{20480}{y^{16}z^{16}} + \frac{51200}{y^{11}z^{17}} = 0.$$

which can be rewritten as

$$5 \left(\left(1 - \frac{16y^2}{z^{10}} \right) \left(1 + \frac{4z^2}{y^{10}} \right) - \frac{20z}{y^5} \left(1 + \frac{4y^2}{z^{10}} \right) \right)^2 \\ - 15^2 \left(1 + \frac{4y^2}{z^{10}} \right) \left(1 + \frac{4z^2}{y^{10}} \right) = 0.$$

Employing (1.6) above, we see that

$$\left(1 - \frac{16y^2}{z^{10}} \right) - 4 \frac{z}{y^5} \frac{\varphi^4(q^5)}{\varphi^4(q)} + 3 \frac{\varphi^2(q^5)}{\varphi^2(q)} = 0.$$

Using (1.8) above, we obtain

$$\left(1 - \frac{16y^2}{z^{10}}\right) + \frac{3y^4}{z^4} \left(\frac{f_2}{f_{10}}\right)^2 - 4\frac{y^3}{z^7} \left(\frac{f_2}{f_{10}}\right)^4 = 0.$$

Further letting, $q \rightarrow -q$ in the preceding expression, we can express $y(-q)$ and $z(-q)$ in terms of f_n using equation (1.7). Subsequently, by multiplying the entire equation by $f_2^2 f_5^{10}$, we arrive at the desired result. \square

Theorem 2.3. *We have*

$$f_1^6 f_5^6 f_{10} + 5f_2^8 f_5^4 f_{10} - 5q^2 f_1^4 f_{10}^9 - 6f_1 f_2^5 f_5^7 = 0.$$

Proof. Multiplying (1.5) throughout by $-5y^{-20}z^{-20}(5y^{12} + y^{10}z^{10} - 10z^{11}y^5 - 40y^7z + 80y^2z^2 + 19z^{12})$ we obtain,

$$\begin{aligned} 5 + \frac{200z^2}{z^{10}} + \frac{20y^2}{z^{10}} + \frac{1050}{z^8 y^8} - \frac{60z}{y^5} - \frac{240z^3}{y^{15}} - \frac{240}{z^9 y^3} - \frac{960}{y^{13} z^7} + \frac{95z^4}{y^{20}} \\ - \frac{1120}{z^6 y^{18}} - \frac{6400}{z^{16} y^{16}} + \frac{800}{z^{18} y^6} - \frac{25y^4}{z^{20}} = 0. \end{aligned}$$

which can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} 5 \left(1 - \frac{6z}{y^5}\right)^2 \left(1 + \frac{4a^2}{z^{10}}\right) \left(1 + \frac{4z^2}{y^{10}}\right)^2 \\ - \left(\left(\frac{25z^2}{y^{10}}\right) \left(1 + \frac{4y^2}{z^{10}}\right) - \frac{5y^2}{z^{10}} \left(1 + \frac{4z^2}{y^{10}}\right)\right) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Employing (1.6) above, we see that

$$\left(1 - \frac{6z}{y^5}\right) - \frac{5z^2}{y^{10}} \frac{\varphi^2(q)}{\varphi^2(q^5)} - \frac{5y^2}{z^{10}} \frac{\varphi^2(q^5)}{\varphi^2(q)} = 0.$$

Using (1.8) above, we obtain

$$\left(1 - \frac{6z}{y^5}\right) + \frac{5}{y^2 z^2} \left(\frac{f_2}{f_{10}}\right)^2 - \frac{5}{y^2 z^6} \left(\frac{f_{10}}{f_2}\right)^2 = 0.$$

Further letting, $q \rightarrow -q$ in the preceding expression, we can express $y(-q)$ and $z(-q)$ in terms of f_n using equation (1.7). Subsequently, by multiplying the entire equation by $f_1^6 f_5^6 f_{10}$, we arrive at the desired result. \square

Theorem 2.4. *We have*

$$4f_2^7 f_5^7 + 5f_1^9 f_5^2 f_{10}^3 - 80q^2 f_1^3 f_2^2 f_{10}^9 - 9f_1^5 f_2^2 f_5^6 f_{10} = 0.$$

Proof. Multiplying (1.5) throughout by $4y^{-2}z^{30}(20y^{12} - 11y^{10}z^{10} - 40y^5z^{11} - 160y^7z + 320y^2z^2 + 16z^{12})$ we obtain,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{44y^{18}}{z^{10}} - \frac{124y^{20}}{z^{20}} - \frac{4560y^{10}}{z^{18}} + \frac{80y^{22}}{z^{30}} - \frac{2560y^{12}}{z^{28}} + \frac{20480y^2}{z^{26}} - \frac{340y^8}{z^8} \\ + \frac{72y^{13}}{z^9} + \frac{288y^{15}}{z^{19}} + \frac{288y^3}{z^7} + \frac{1152y^5}{z^{17}} - \frac{64}{y^2 z^6} - \frac{256}{z^{16}} = 0, \end{aligned}$$

which can be rewritten as

$$5 \left(\frac{5y^9}{z^5} \left(1 + \frac{4y^2}{z^{10}} \right) - \frac{16y^{11}}{z^{15}} \left(1 + \frac{4z^2}{y^{10}} \right) \right)^2 - \left(\frac{9y^9}{z^5} - \frac{4y^4}{z^4} \right)^2 \left(1 + \frac{4y^2}{z^{10}} \right) \left(1 + \frac{4z^2}{y^{10}} \right) = 0.$$

Employing (1.6) above, we see that

$$\frac{5y^9}{z^5} - \frac{80y^{11}}{z^{15}} \frac{\varphi^4(q^5)}{\varphi^4(q)} - \frac{y^4}{z^4} \left(\frac{9y^5}{z} - 4 \right) \frac{\varphi^2(q^5)}{\varphi^2(q)} = 0.$$

Using (1.8) above, we obtain

$$\frac{5y^9}{z^5} - 80q^{4/3} \frac{y^3}{z^7} \left(\frac{f_{10}}{f_2} \right)^4 - q^{2/3} \left(\frac{9y^5}{z} - 4 \right) \left(\frac{f_{10}}{f_2} \right)^2 = 0.$$

Further letting, $q \rightarrow -q$ in the preceding expression, we can express $y(-q)$ and $z(-q)$ in terms of f_n using equation (1.7). Subsequently, by multiplying the entire equation by $f_2^7 f_5^7$, we arrive at the desired result. \square

Theorem 2.5. *We have*

$$f_1^{10} f_{10}^2 + 100q f_1^3 f_2^3 f_5^3 f_{10}^3 + 15f_1^6 f_2^2 f_5^4 - 16f_2^{10} f_5^2 = 0.$$

Proof. Multiplying (1.5) throughout by $20y^{-20} z^{-20} (4y^{12} - 11y^{10} z^{10} - 32y^{11} z^5 - 128yz^7 - 64y^2 z^2 - 64z^{12})$ we obtain,

$$\begin{aligned} -220 - \frac{200y}{z^5} - \frac{1060z^2}{y^{10}} + \frac{1140y^2}{z^{10}} + \frac{11120}{z^8 y^8} + \frac{2400}{y^9 z^3} + \frac{80y^4}{z^{20}} - \frac{2560}{y^6 z^{18}} - \frac{800y^3}{z^{15}} \\ + \frac{9600}{y^7 z^{13}} + \frac{1280z^4}{y^{20}} + \frac{42240}{z^6 y^{18}} + \frac{12800}{zy^{19}} + \frac{20480}{y^{16} z^{16}} + \frac{51200}{z^{11} y^{17}} = 0. \end{aligned}$$

which can be rewritten as

$$5 \left(\left(1 - \frac{16z^2}{y^{10}} \right) \left(1 + \frac{4y^2}{z^{10}} \right) + \frac{20y}{z^5} \left(1 + \frac{4z^2}{y^{10}} \right) \right)^2 + 15^2 \left(1 + \frac{4y^2}{z^{10}} \right) \left(1 + \frac{4z^2}{y^{10}} \right) = 0.$$

Employing (1.6) above, we see that

$$\left(1 - \frac{16z^2}{y^{10}} \right) - 100 \frac{y}{z^5} \frac{\varphi^4(q^5)}{\varphi^4(q)} + 15 \frac{\varphi^2(q^5)}{\varphi^2(q)} = 0.$$

Using (1.8) above, we obtain

$$\left(1 - \frac{16z^2}{y^{10}} \right) - 100 \frac{z^3}{y^7} \left(\frac{f_{10}}{f_2} \right)^4 + 15 \frac{y^4}{z^4} \left(\frac{f_{10}}{f_2} \right)^2 = 0.$$

Further letting, $q \rightarrow -q$ in the preceding expression, we can express $y(-q)$ and $z(-q)$ in terms of f_n using equation (1.7). Subsequently, by multiplying the entire equation by $f_1^{10} f_{10}^2$, we arrive at the desired result. \square

Theorem 2.6. *We have*

$$f_2^2 f_5^{10} - 3q f_2^4 f_5^2 f_{10}^6 - f_1^3 f_2^3 f_5^3 f_{10}^3 - q^2 f_1^2 f_{10}^{10} = 0.$$

Proof. Multiplying (1.5) throughout by $5y^{-20}z^{-20}(y^{12} - y^{10}z^{10} + 8z^{11}y^5 + 32y^7z - 44y^2z^2 - 16z^{12})$ we obtain,

$$\begin{aligned} 5 + \frac{695}{y^8 z^8} - \frac{10y^2}{z^{10}} + \frac{164z^2}{y^{10}} - \frac{150}{y^3 z^9} + \frac{80z^4}{y^{20}} - \frac{1060}{z^6 y^{18}} - \frac{200z^3}{y^{15}} - \frac{600}{y^{13} z^7} + \frac{5y^4}{z^{20}} \\ + \frac{1140}{y^6 z^{18}} + \frac{200}{yz^{19}} - \frac{3520}{y^{16} z^{16}} + \frac{800}{y^{11} z^7} - \frac{50z}{y^5} = 0. \end{aligned}$$

which can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} 5 \left(\left(1 - \frac{y^2}{z^{10}} \right) \left(1 + \frac{4z^2}{y^{10}} \right) - \frac{5z}{y^5} \left(1 + \frac{4y^2}{z^{10}} \right) \right)^2 \\ - \left(\frac{15}{y^4 z^4} \right)^2 \left(1 + \frac{4y^2}{z^{10}} \right) \left(1 + \frac{4z^2}{y^{10}} \right) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Employing (1.6) above, we see that

$$\left(1 - \frac{y^2}{z^{10}} \right) - \frac{z}{y^5} \frac{\varphi^4(q)}{\varphi^4(q^5)} + \frac{3}{y^4 z^4} \frac{\varphi^2(q)}{\varphi^2(q^5)} = 0.$$

Using (1.8) above, we obtain

$$\left(1 - \frac{y^2}{z^{10}} \right) + \frac{3}{z^8} \left(\frac{f_2}{f_{10}} \right)^2 - \frac{y^3}{z^7} \left(\frac{f_2}{f_{10}} \right)^4 = 0.$$

Further letting, $q \rightarrow -q$ in the preceding expression, we can express $y(-q)$ and $z(-q)$ in terms of f_n using equation (1.7). Subsequently, by multiplying the entire equation by $f_2^2 f_5^{10}$, we arrive at the desired result. \square

3. Partition Results

The above given Somos identities has an application in the theory of partitions. This was first developed by Haung and chen [4, 5] for Göllintz-Gordon functions. Now we define colored partition as given

“A positive integer n has l colors if there are l copies of n available colors and all of them are viewed as distinct objects. Partitions of a positive integer into parts with colors are colored partitions”. For instance if 3 colors are assigned to 1, then the possible colored partitions of 2 are $1_b + 1_b$, $1_y + 1_y$, $1_i + 1_i$, $1_b + 1_y$, $1_b + 1_i$, $1_i + 1_y$ and 2, where we utilized the indices b (blue), y (yellow) and i (indigo) to recognize three colors of 1. For our convenience, we use the notation,

$$(q^{r\pm}; q^s)_\infty := (q^r, q^{s-r}; q^s)_\infty, \quad (r < s); r, s \in \mathbb{N}. \quad (3.1)$$

As an example of this, $(q^{3\pm}; q^8)_\infty$ means $(q^3, q^5; q^8)_\infty$, which is $(q^3; q^8)_\infty (q^5; q^8)_\infty$. Also the number of partitions of t where all the parts are congruent to l modulo m with n colors is given by the generating function as $\frac{1}{(q^l; q^m)_\infty^n}$.

Theorem 3.1. *Let $\zeta_1(t)$ represent the divisions of t split into components that are congruent to ± 2 modulo 10 with 7 colors and $+5$ modulo 10 with 8 colors. Let $\zeta_2(t)$ is chosen to represent the divisions of t split into components that are congruent to ± 1 modulo 10 with 8 colors, ± 2 modulo 10 with 1 colors and $+5$ modulo 10 with 16 colors. Let $\zeta_3(t)$ represent the divisions of t split into components that are congruent to ± 1 modulo 10 with 9 colors and $+5$ modulo 10 with 12 colors. Let $\zeta_4(t)$ is taken to represent the divisions of t split into components that are congruent to ± 1 modulo 10 with 8 colors, ± 2 modulo 10 with 3 colors. Then we have*

$$\zeta_1(t) - 16\zeta_2(t-1) + 24\zeta_3(t) - 25\zeta_4(t) = 0, \quad t \geq 1.$$

Proof. On using (1.7) in Theorem 2.1, dividing throughout by $f_1^9 f_2^7 f_3^8 f_5^6$ and then simplifying subject to the common base q^{10} , we deduce that

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{(q_7^2, q_7^4, q_8^5, q_7^6, q_7^8; q^{10})_\infty} - \frac{16q}{(q_8^1, q^2, q_8^3, q^4, q_{16}^5, q_8^7, q^8, q_8^9; q^{10})_\infty} \\ & + \frac{24}{(q_9^1, q_9^3, q_{12}^5, q_9^7, q_9^9; q^{10})_\infty} - \frac{25}{(q_8^1, q_3^2, q_8^3, q_3^4, q_3^6, q_8^7, q_3^8, q_8^9; q^{10})_\infty} = 0. \end{aligned}$$

On using (3.1) in the above, we have

$$\frac{1}{(q_7^{2\pm}, q_8^{5+}; q^{10})_\infty} - \frac{16q}{(q_8^{1\pm}, q_1^{2\pm}, q_{16}^{5+}; q^{10})_\infty} + \frac{24}{(q_9^{1\pm}, q_{12}^{5+}; q^{10})_\infty} - \frac{25}{(q_8^{1\pm}, q_3^{2\pm}; q^{10})_\infty} = 0. \quad (3.2)$$

We observe that (3.3) gives the generating functions for $\zeta_1(t)$, $\zeta_2(t)$, $\zeta_3(t)$ and $\zeta_4(t)$ respectively. Hence the above identity is equivalent to

$$\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \zeta_1(t)q^t - 16 \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \zeta_2(t)q^{t+1} + 24 \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \zeta_3(t)q^t - 25 \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \zeta_4(t)q^t = 0$$

and we set $\zeta_1(0) = \zeta_2(0) = \zeta_3(0) = \zeta_4(0) = 1$. Now on extracting terms of q^t in the above, we obtain the required result. \square

Example: For $t = 1$, the partition representations are given by the following table.

$\zeta_1(1) = 0 :$
$\zeta_2(0) = 1 :$
$\zeta_3(1) = 9 : \quad 1_r, 1_w, 1_{bl}, 1_g, 1_y, 1_o, 1_p, 1_v, 1_b$
$\zeta_4(2) = 8 : \quad 1_r, 1_w, 1_{bl}, 1_g, 1_y, 1_o, 1_p, 1_v$

Theorem 3.2. *Let $\zeta_1(t)$ represent the divisions of t split into components that are congruent to ± 1 modulo 10 with 4 colors and ± 2 modulo 10 with 1 colors. Let $\zeta_2(t)$ is chosen to represent the divisions of t split into components that are congruent to ± 2 modulo 10 with 3 colors. Let $\zeta_3(t)$ represent the divisions of t split into components that are congruent to ± 1 modulo 10 with 2 colors, ± 2 modulo 10 with 3 colors and $+5$ modulo 10 with 8 colors. Let $\zeta_4(t)$ is taken to represent the divisions of t split into components that are congruent to ± 1 modulo 10 with 1 color, $+5$ modulo 10 with 4 colors. Then we have*

$$\zeta_1(t) + 3\zeta_2(t) - 16\zeta_3(t-2) - 4\zeta_4(t) = 0, \quad t \geq 2.$$

Proof. On using (1.7) in Theorem 2.2, dividing throughout by $f_1^4 f_2^3 f_5^{10} f_{10}^{10}$ and then simplifying subject to the common base q^{10} , we deduce that

$$\frac{1}{(q_4^1, q_4^2, q_4^3, q_4^4, q_4^6, q_4^7, q_4^8, q_4^9; q^{10})_\infty} + \frac{3}{(q_3^2, q_3^4, q_3^6, q_3^8; q^{10})_\infty} - \frac{16q^2}{(q_2^1, q_2^2, q_2^3, q_2^4, q_2^5, q_2^6, q_2^7, q_2^8, q_2^9; q^{10})_\infty} - \frac{4}{(q^1, q^3, q^5, q^7, q^9; q^{10})_\infty} = 0.$$

On using (3.1) in the above, we have

$$\frac{1}{(q_4^{1\pm}, q_4^{2\pm}; q^{10})_\infty} + \frac{3}{(q_3^{2\pm}; q^{10})_\infty} - \frac{16q^2}{(q_2^{1\pm}, q_2^{2\pm}, q_2^{5+}; q^{10})_\infty} - \frac{4}{(q^{1\pm}, q_4^{5+}; q^{10})_\infty} = 0. \tag{3.3}$$

We observe that (3.3) gives the generating functions for $\zeta_1(t)$, $\zeta_2(t)$, $\zeta_3(t)$ and $\zeta_4(t)$ respectively. Hence the above identity is equivalent to

$$\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \zeta_1(t)q^t + 3 \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \zeta_2(t)q^t - 16 \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \zeta_3(t)q^{t+2} - 4 \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \zeta_4(t)q^t = 0$$

and we set $\zeta_1(0) = \zeta_2(0) = \zeta_3(0) = \zeta_4(0) = 1$. Now on extracting terms of q^t in the above, we obtain the required result. \square

Example: For $t = 2$, the partition representations are given by the following table.

$\zeta_1(2) = 11 :$	$1_r + 1_r, 1_w + 1_w, 1_y + 1_y, 1_b + 1_b, 1_r + 1_w, 1_r + 1_b, 1_r + 1_y,$ $1_r + 1_b, 1_r + 1_y, 1_b + 1_y, 2_r$
$\zeta_2(2) = 3 :$	$3_r, 3_g, 3_b$
$\zeta_3(0) = 1 :$	
$\zeta_4(2) = 1 :$	$1_r + 1_r$

Conclusion The below mentioned are some Somos's eta-function identities of similar kind of level 10 :

$$\begin{aligned} f_1^6 f_5^6 + 6q f_1^3 f_2 f_5^3 f_{10}^3 - f_2^8 f_5^4 + q^2 f_1^4 f_{10}^8 &= 0. \\ f_1^2 f_2 f_5^5 f_{10} + q f_1^6 f_{10} + 4q f_1 f_2^5 f_5 f_{10}^5 - f_2^6 f_5^5 &= 0. \\ f_2^5 f_5^7 + 4f_1^5 f_5^6 f_{10} - 20q^2 f_1^3 f_{10}^9 - 5f_1^4 f_2^3 f_5^3 f_{10}^2 &= 0. \\ f_1^8 f_{10}^4 + 24f_1^3 f_2^5 f_5 f_{10}^3 + 80q f_2^6 f_{10}^6 - 25f_2^4 f_5^8 &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

and many more. Ramanujan's modular equation of degree 5 has been utilized to prove the above identities and colored partitions are also developed to verify the results as an application.

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